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Short-term field-study programmes for developing interdisciplinary skills in engineering education

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ABSTRACT

Short-term field study involves groups of students working in an off-campus (sometimes international) setting, and often involves working on realistic, open-ended problems, in interaction with a host community. Such learning experiences are intended to develop skills and knowledge needed for working across cultures and contexts and in interdisciplinary teams. One aspect of such programs which requires particular attention is their potential to take students out of their 'comfort zone', thereby enabling them to question their previously taken-for-granted assumptions. Fully exploiting such opportunities requires considering the role of social and human sciences in such programmes for engineering students. Here we analyse four case studies of short-term field study programmes in engineering education. While there are differences in location (Switzerland, China, Russia, Colombia), and in the nature of the projects, they share a methodology of mixing student disciplines and skills, interaction with people from other cultures or contexts, physically moving to a fieldwork location radically different from a classroom setting, and the use of reflection tools drawn from social and human sciences. Conclusions are drawn from this as to the possibilities, issues and challenges in short-term field studies in engineering education.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Engaging engineering students with cultural differences

Engineering educators have increasingly worked to include some culturally different, often international, element as part of the training offered to engineering students. In some countries, like France for example, an obligatory international placement (either in the form of academic mobility or as an international work placement) is strongly encouraged by engineering accreditation agencies [1]. Such placements are seen as important in ensuring engineers develop an understanding of cultural diversity and of the way in which culture impacts on the work of the engineer. Although there is a growing recognition of the importance of such international placements, not all countries have normalized the practice: in the US, for example, it has been estimated that as few as 3% of engineering students study abroad (as compared to some 20% of social science and business/management students) [2].

Students who have participated in international experiences in their training have been found to have experienced a number of benefits. For example, an increase in participants' intercultural sensitivity has been found in a number of studies [3], as has a sense of ethical sensitivity (or 'global citizenship' development) [4]. There seems to be relatively few studies that look at the experience of engineering students during such international experiences, but some studies specifically with engineering students have linked such study abroad opportunities with increased capacity to work in teams as well as with increased intercultural sensitivity [5].

One important dimension of being confronted with alterity in the form of different social and cultural systems is that it can highlight that things the student may well have thought of as being 'normal', are often in fact phenomena of their own culture. Such 'decentring' experiences can be unsettling for students but also open the possibility to broaden their understanding. Some engineering educators have recently adopted the concept of 'liminality' to explain these opportunities [8]: the term 'liminal' (long used in Anthropology) derives from the Latin word for 'threshold', and indicates a sense of 'in-betweenness', of being in a process of transition in which new understandings and ways of thinking are becoming possible, and in which a new status is being socially ascribed. Liminal experiences are sometimes uncomfortable and emotionally challenging for learners as well as being potentially rewarding in terms of new learning; as such, the concept of liminality draws attention to the 'whole body' nature of the learning experience which encompasses physical and emotional experiences as well as intellectual ones.

1.2 Field studies

Central to the idea of such (dis)placements is the idea that students can learn something important from *experiencing* (as distinct to simply hearing or reading about) [6] a different cultural, social, economic and linguistic context. Indeed, it is worth noting that students may not have to engage in international travel to experience a social context radically different from their own; such differences can often be found in communities on the very doorstep of their own university.

One teaching methodology associated with this idea of experiential learning is the *field study*, defined as providing students with opportunities to learn through active involvement in “realistic” professional experiences as well as in opportunities for them to study and reflect on those experiences [7]. In social scientific disciplines like Sociology or Anthropology students often learn the analytical and research methods of the discipline through doing field research and reflecting on this experience. This practice has been translated into a signature teaching and learning strategy for professional training in disciplines which draw heavily on such social scientific disciplines, including social work and teaching. There is something to be gained in the education of engineering professionals by learning from the experiences of education in these other professional domains.

There are, however, few studies [e.g., 2] which provide insight into the issues involved in integrating into engineering education field study opportunities which involve engagement with cultural difference. This paper aims to add to this important area of study.

2 METHODOLOGY

This paper looks at the experience of introducing into engineering education short-term field studies which include an explicit focus on cultural difference and alterity. In common with other studies in this area [2] a case study approach is used. A case study is defined as an empirical enquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon in its real life context using multiple sources of evidence, and in which there are generally more variables of interest than data points [9]. Case studies can be thought of as akin to experiments: rather than being sampled, case studies are *selected* on the basis of particular features that make them interesting. As with multiple experiments, multiple case studies allow for cross case comparison which can rapidly increase the explanatory capacity of the study [10].

This paper is based on an analysis of four different case studies of international experiences offered to engineering students. Initial interviews were conducted with three of the four field study coordinators to explore if there was something meaningful to be gained from a comparative case study approach. Following this, data was collected from each of the four coordinators using a series of open-ended questions which were responded to either in writing (2 coordinators) or in a one-to-one interview setting (2 coordinators). Finally a group interview/discussion with three of the coordinators provided a further opportunities to tease out themes and comparisons.

3 THE CASE STUDIES

3.1 Case study descriptions

The four case studies presented here are offered by the College of Humanities in a mainland European technical university. The four field study coordinators are all social scientists.

Table 1. Overview of the Case study field studies programs

Field location	Lausanne, Switzerland; Bengaluru, India; Shanghai, China	Greater China – Shenzhen and Hong Kong	Russian Arctic and Yamal peninsula	Amazon basin, Leticia City, Colombia
Nature of project/activity in field study location	International summer schools (academic courses and applied field visits)	Applied engineering design project with prototyping activity in China	Academic courses & Field research (e.g. oceanographic research, or civil engineering historical reconstruction)	Scientific & social research or a design project
Typical number of students per group	15-30	24	23	14
Balance between technical university students and those from other schools	75% STEM. Others from Social and Human Sciences, & Asian studies.	50% STEM. Others from Business, Industrial Design & Media Interaction Design.	50% STEM. Others from Social and Human Sciences, Environmental Sciences, Global health, & Law.	40% STEM. Others from Health, & Social and Human Sciences
Length of field study component	6 weeks	2 weeks	3-4 weeks	3 weeks
Integrated into study programme?	16 credits for courses taken when on field study (8 in Lausanne, 8 Asia).	18 credits in total for whole project, of which 4 for the field study component.	18 credits in total for whole project, of which 6 for the field study component.	4 – 6 credits for courses which prepared the project.
Years active	2009-2016	2015-present	2015-present	2018-present

The four case studies are:

- An international summer school programme in which students participated in summer schools in Europe, India and China, studying the history, political

science, anthropology, cultural studies and economics of each location, including field visits and language learning

- A hardware innovation programme, in which students design a connected device in their ‘home’ location, then travel to China to work to produce a prototype
- A Russian Arctic research program, in which students work on oceanographic, historical, and geographical research and documentation projects in the Arctic and Siberia
- An Amazon basin field study, in which students research the effect of urbanisation on indigenous people’s lives focusing on the eco-epidemiology of health or on the development of on-line tools to aid indigenous language learning.

All four have a number of similarities in structure:

- the field study is not a required part of any programme of study (three of the four are integrated into an optional minor which can be taken as part of a student’s degree programme)
- the field study involves a visit to a location which is culturally and linguistically different from their place of study
- engineering and science students participate in the field study alongside students from other disciplines, drawn from other universities
- students undertake a project (typically either an engineering design project, or a research project which involves some combination of social and natural sciences);
- while much of the project work is completed in their ‘home’ university, (either before or after the field study trip) some of the project work is completed while in the field study location
- reflective activities while in the field study location provide an important part of the learning in the field study.

A number of issues and challenges have been experienced by those responsible for the programmes. These are described below.

3.2 Embedding in a curriculum

All of the field study experiences described here involve substantial investment from students. At a minimum the students are required to invest time during the summer to travel to the field study location and to work while there. Students generally also pay a portion of the travel and accommodation costs associated with the trip. Not all of the institutions involved, however, offer the same academic credit for participation in the field study. Where the field study itself is not assigned significant credits, it seems to be regarded as being, in itself, a reward for this investment: as one of the co-ordinators put it, “...*the trip itself was viewed as the reward. The idea of the school was very much [to say to the student] ‘you get a free trip to China, so you should do the work required [by the project] for free [i.e., without getting academic credit]’*”.

In the early experiences of field study trips in the technical university, there also seemed to be a resistance on the part of the school to assign credits to the field study in the same way as they would be assigned to traditional courses. Sometimes this was explained in terms of administrative reasons – since the field study trips took place during the summer, did not fit into a spring or autumn semester and could not meet the same grading deadlines as other courses, it was assumed that academic credits could not be awarded. Although many of the students who participated at that time engaged fully with the program the lack of associated academic credit meant that some students did not approach the field study diligently. This remains the case for institutions where academic credit is not awarded, including, in at least one case, a student dropping out at the last minute, with potentially serious knock on effects on other students in the same project group. At a minimum, the ‘voluntary’ nature of the student engagement places significant additional pressure on coordinators who are left in the role of having to negotiate with students their commitment to group project activities.

Establishing the field study within a formal academic structure which involved earning academic credit was therefore an important development. This had a number of elements: first the field study needed to establish a track record which justified its inclusion. This meant that newer field studies (such as the Amazon basin program) had to establish the value of their learning by running for a number of years without significant academic credit before being accepted as ‘creditworthy’. It is notable that this is a higher bar than is set for traditional courses offered (which typically received academic approval on the basis of a short written description rather than having to be first offered without credit). Once accepted, the ECTS calculation of circa 2 credits per working week was applied to provide a ‘justifiable’ credit weighting for the field study (as in the China and Russian Arctic field studies). A solution to the ‘grading deadline’ problem was also found once the learning from the field studies had been sufficiently verified. That solutions to administrative difficulties were found suggests that it was the perceived legitimacy of the experience within student’s education which was actually at question all along.

The challenges of embedding in the curriculum are increased when multiple universities are involved. Within those field studies that are currently embedded in a curriculum (the China and Russian Arctic field studies) in the technical university, two different models of doing this emerged. In the case of the China program, each university managed the process differently, with, for example, different weights being assigned to the field study in different institutions. As a result, students were sometimes doing similar work for different credit. As noted above, this puts additional pressure on coordinators who are left in the role of having to negotiate learning activities with students. In the Russian field study, a single model for the program was developed and offered to different partner universities who either chose to ‘buy-in’ or not. Perhaps because the program was perceived as prestigious, this did not have a negative impact on student uptake.

3.3 Framing activities of the field study

The first model used for confronting students with alterity was the international summer school model. This ran for seven years and was highly valued by students. Running such a program required a very high degree of additional investment by faculty when compared to more traditional courses, and this contributed to the program being halted.

One of the features of a field study is that the students are engaged in a realistic professional activity. The China, and Russia (and later Amazon) experiences might be thought of as a shift towards a 'field study' model in that the students are involved in either a design activity, a scientific research activity, or in some mix of the two. This shift has probably made it easier to 'legitimate' the field study in that the framing activity through which students learn is more clearly an 'engineering' activity. At the same time, it also poses potential difficulties in that the practice itself becomes central to the experience and reflection on that practice runs the risk of being marginalised. This, again, requires considerable input and skill from the coordinator to ensure that the reflective activities are not lost.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

It is clear that field studies can play an important role in enabling engineering students to learn through experiencing engineering and scientific practices in different social and cultural settings, and reflecting on those experiences. Such experiences can allow students to understand how disciplines are constituted in different countries, what a notion or concept means in a different setting, and what are the relations between a topic and educational policies in different settings (i.e. in a broader sense, the relations between the State and its education and research institutions). Embedding these experiences in an already crowded curriculum however, is not without its challenges.

First, the field studies discussed here differ from traditional courses. They do not follow the same timetable, or the same semester structure, and their experiential nature means that what and how students learn may be hard to describe in advance within the limitations of a taxonomy of cognitive outcomes. All of this meant that the bar to be accepted within the academic program seems higher for field studies than is the case for more traditional courses. Embedding within the formal program does, however, appear to be worthwhile, given the challenges for coordinators raised by more ad hoc solutions. Part of this embedding may involve the use of 'realistic' engineering practices as framing activities for the field study. This shift can involve risks for learning however, as retaining a focus on reflection in the field study may become a challenge.

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